

The Impact Of Using Outsourcing On Job Performance: The Moderating Roles Of Organizational Structure And Organizational Culture

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 19, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: June 21, 2024</p> <p>Keywords : Job Performance, Outsourcing, Organizational Structure, Organizational Culture, Telecommunication</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12208481</p>	<p><i>This research paper aims to explore how the outsourcing in the telecommunication sector affects organizational performance through examining the mediation role of organizational structure and organizational culture. To this end, a conceptual framework of relevant research factors was utilized according to the extant literature. A sample of 72 employees was utilized and an instrument of 20 items was used in this study. Structural equation modelling with AMOS 21.0 was utilized to test the proposed research hypotheses. The findings of analysis demonstrated the outsourcing was significant in predicting both organizational structure and organizational culture, thus improving job performance. Moreover, organizational structure and organizational culture play a significant mediating influence on the path linking of outsourcing to job performance. Discussion, conclusion and future work are stated at the end of this work.</i></p>

Introduction

Outsourcing is one of the important pillars which influence job performance. It also considered one of the effective tools enhancing employees' job performance (Lee et al., 2019). Outsourcing is useful for giving employees ability to conduct their functions and increase job productivity (Al-Qudah et al., 2020). In spite of, the using of outsourcing is considered a problem for the most of companies because of the negative consequences on employee job satisfaction (Lee et al., 2019; Almajali, 2019). based on research and development in outsourcing area have led to focus and give more attention on the effects of outsourcing on the organizational structure and culture through measuring the outsourcing effects on employee knowledge in order to reach a positive impact on increasing employee job satisfaction and thus developing job performance (Al-Junidi, 2020; Hanandeh, 2018, Barakat, 2015).

organization structure is closely related to the usage of outsourcing, because outsource some tasks within the company need to renew the organization structure (Al-Junidi, 2020), while organization culture is representing all habits, work standards, values and behaviours that mutual between the employees of company (Al-Junidi, 2020). Previous research and studies have recommended that organization structure and organization culture effects on job performance (Burke, 2017).

That's why; the research study defines the organizational structure and culture factors which can influence job performance. This research is different from other researches in discussing two main points. First, this research measures and examines the effects of organizational structure and culture as main mediators on job performance. Even a lot of studies studied the effects of organization structure and organization culture in performance as whole, no research taken organization structure and culture as mediating roles between using outsourcing and its effects on job performance. Second, the research study is considered the first study which measures the effects of outsourcing on job performance through using large data in three of the telecommunication firms in Jordan. The research adds more literature by defining outsourcing, organizational structure and organization culture based on collected data and information of this research. Finally, this research gives clear information about how job performance is developed from using outsourcing, via measuring outsourcing effects on organization structure and organization culture.

1. Research Theory and Hypotheses

Based on knowledge management theory and human resource theory, this study builds a research model which explains the relationship between outsourcing and job performance through taking the moderating roles of outsourcing on organization structure and organization culture. Note that taking organization structure and organization culture is considered mediating roles with taking and measuring the effects of outsourcing on enhancing employee knowledge (Figure 1). Based on

knowledge and human resource theory, using new knowledge and new experts within a specific environment can give employee ability to learn it, share it as a team that can affect rapidly on the organization environment as whole, and it could improve employees performance in doing their jobs (Zhang et al, 2011; Gonget al., 2013; Chuang et al., 2016; Akbari & Ghaffari, 2017, Hanandeh, 2017, Barakat, 2011; Al-Zagaier, 2015).Based on that, this study suggested that outsourcing effects positively on job performance by measuring it is effects on developing the organization structure and organization culture. All the research study concepts and model suggestions are discussed in the following figure.

Figure (1): the research conceptual model

1.1 Outsourcing and Job Performance

Outsourcing is one of the firms' tool which most of the firms resort to use in order to enhance the business processes efficiency and effectiveness, and apply best and success practices for other firms (Lee et al., 2019). Organizational performance has been defined as one of the managerial concepts which contain a set of approaches that represent and evaluate the organizational overall performance (Rainey, 2014; Andersen et al., 2016). In 2019, Lee and their colleagues studied the effects of using outsourcing on job performance in public and private sectors through using transaction cost economics (TCE), principal-agent problem, public service motivation (PSM), psychological contract, and job satisfaction in order to measure the effects on job performance which effects positively in job performance. Furthermore, the effects of employees' knowledge on job performance can be realized on their behaviours and attitudes which can effect and influence the organizational and job performance (Rainey, 2014; Andersen et al, 2016; Lee et al., 2019). In addition, outsourcing is one of the important pillars which influence job performance (Lee et al., 2019). Also, Outsourcing is representing an important tool for enhancing employees' job performance (Lee et al., 2019). At the same time, previous studies showed that using outsourcing is useful for giving employees ability to conduct their functions and increase job productivity (Lee et al., 2019). In (2019), Olajumoke et al., analysed and discussed using outsourcing on job and organization performance by taking the analysis of 51 empirical research in 24 articles and discuss their results to determine exactly the relationship and effects of outsourcing on job and organization performance; the result shown that outsourcing has a strong effect on enhancing job and organization performance. Based on justifications and information on the above the first hypothesis is derived as the following:

H1: Outsourcing will have significant positive impact on job performance.

2.2 Outsourcing and Organizational Structure

Over the past decade, outsourcing approved it is efficiency as an effective and appropriate strategic choice for companies through enhancing the organization structure within the manufacturing department (Momme, 2002). Burke (2017) agreed that outsourcing can be effective solution in enhancing organization structure main attributes. The first attribute that drives organization structure is the centralization, which related to the decision-making process within the firm that given always to the executive manager or to the strategic executive level (Burke, 2017). The research study aims to measure if the effects of outsourcing could change the decision-making process within the company. The second attribute of the organizational structure is the formalization which refers to the organization policies and regulations (Burke, 2017; Mishra et al., 2016). The research study aims to measure how using outsourcing could develop the organization policies and regulations. The third attribute for the organizational structure is the

standardization that represents the organizational process rules and guides which control organization employees during executing process of activities (Harper, 2015; Burke, 2017; Mishra et al., 2016). The research study aims to measure if using outsourcing can improve organization processes standards. The last attribute is specialization which defined as the division degree of the organization's labour and job's distributions (Mishra et al., 2016). Furthermore, moreover, the rapid changes and strong competition forced firms to find more new ways for meeting challenges in the organizational structure, management practice, and the way of leading as main elements which effects on employees and their abilities to do their jobs (Masa'deh et al., 2016). Kamali (2014) agreed that in order to enhance job performance the firm should have a flexible structure which allow for employees to share knowledge easily that will effect on most of organization factors such as strategies, visions, resources use, performing jobs which can enhance the job performance and overall performance. in the last, using outsourcing can effect positively or negatively on job performance based on the nature of organization structure, because organizational structure is represented an important factors that play an effective role on giving employees the ability to learn new knowledge, share it between them, and reuse it to conduct their jobs well (Harper, 2015; Burke, 2017; Mishra et al., 2016). The research study aims to measure the effectiveness of using outsourcing in enhancing organization structure as a mediator role could enhance job performance. Based on justifications and information on the above the second, third, and fourth hypotheses are derived as the following :

H2: Outsourcing will have significant positive impact on organizational structure.

H3: Organizational structure will have significant positive impact on job performances.

H4: Organization structure fully mediates the outsourcing effects on job performance.

2.3 Outsourcing and organization Culture

Organization culture is defined as a company characteristic such as values, departments, habits, and beliefs that represents the current situation of specific company within specific period of time (Arayesh et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2011). The importance of organizational culture shown clearly in enhancing and developing business processes (Borekci et al., 2014) . Popoli (2017), defined three main dimension of the organizational culture: the first dimension is the degree of path dependency which assumed that the organization employee's attitudes and way of doing jobs can be developed based on the new information that they received and learned, the second dimension of the organization culture is the uncertainty avoidance which refers to the ability of organization employees to work and communicate within unstable environment and conditions through reducing uncertainty and suspicions, and the third dimension is the trust that means the ability of the organization in embedding the values of credibility, respect, fair treatment, and interaction. many studies defined the relationship between organizational culture and business performance strategies, and organizational change, but few studies and researches entered deeply in studying the effects of using outsourcing on improving organizational culture (Boyce et al., 2015; Naranjo et al., 2016; Chih |& Yang, 2011; Hock et al., 2016; Omazić and Sopta, 2017; Engelen et al., 2014; Iljins et al., 2015).Therese research study aims to give more information and details related with the effectiveness of using outsourcing in enhancing organization culture as a mediator role which could lead to better job performance. In 2018, Theresia et al.studied the relationship and the effect of the organizational culture on enhancing job performance through distributing 180 questionnaires in set of universities, based on results job performance was good enough when the organizational culture is considered flexible and effective. Furthermore, in 2019 Kyoung and Sunyoung studied how if the organizational culture is learning and intelligent culture could effect on improving job performance, the findings of the study indicated that the organizational learning culture and the way of leading can effect positively on job performance.

A lot of researches studied the effect of outsourcing on job performance with taking the effect and the role of organizational culture as catalyst element, most of researches findings indicated that using outsourcing could improve job performance if using outsourcing effect on organization capabilities such as employee knowledge, firm capabilities, and organizational structure and culture; and in order to enhance job performance the firm management has to measure the effects of each step of using outsourcing on the organization capabilities and pillars (Hendry, 1995; Theresia et al., 2018; Hammouri, 2018; Kyoung N. & Sunyoung, 2019, Al-Junidi, 2020). Based on information on the above the fifth, sixth, and seventh hypotheses are derived as the following :

H5: Outsourcing will have significant positive impact on organizational culture.

H6: Organizational culture will have significant positive impact on job performance.

H7: Organization culture fully mediates the outsourcing effects on job performance.

3. Methodology

The targeted population for this study was marketing employees in three of the largest telecommunication companies in Jordan. The firms selected for this study are three leading institutions in the Jordanian telecommunication sector: orange, umniah, and zain. A questionnaire survey was implemented to capture

the required data to explore the effects of using outsourcing on job performance. The questionnaire divided into three parts: The first part included an introduction about the study to ensure that employees understand what/why they are filling the survey. The second part of the survey collected the personal information of the employees. The final part included 20 items derived from previous empirical studies in such area as shown in Table 1. Out of 87 questionnaires distributed to a convenient sample of marketing employees in total, 72 valid questionnaires were returned and approved for data analysis. Such number indicates a good response rate of 83%. The demographics of the sample used are depicted in Table 2. Descriptive statistics revealed that majority of respondents are male (68%) and between 26-35 years old (36%). The majority of them are Bachelor degree holders (78%) with less than 3 years' experience (29%).

Table 1: Variables and Item Codes

Variable	Item Codes	Sources
Outsourcing	(OUT1), (OUT2), (OUT3), (OUT4), (OUT5)	Tenkorang (2016)
Organizational Structure	(OS1), (OS2), (OS3), (OS4), (OS5)	Arumbarkah (2020)
Organizational Culture	(OC1), (OC2), (OC3), (OC4), (OC5)	Kawiana et al., (2018)
Job Performance	(JP1), (JP2), (JP3), (JP4), (JP5)	Natasaputra & Kusumastuti (2016)

Table 2: Sample Demographics

Age			Experience			Gender		
Category	Freq.	%	Category	Freq.	%	Category	Freq.	%
18-25	7	10	Less than 3 years	21	29	Male	49	68
26-35	26	36	3 years	18	25	Female	23	32
36-44	25	35	6 years	19	27	Total	72	100
Age > 44	14	19	More than 6 years	14	19			
Total	72	100	Total	72	100			
Education			Telecommunication Sector					
Category	Freq.	%	Category	Freq.	%			
Diploma	11	15	Umniah	22	30			
Bachelor	56	78	Zain	20	28			
Postgraduate	5	7	Orange	30	42			
Total	72	100	Total	72	100			

4. Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Measurement Model

Before the hypothesized structural model is tested, we have to measure the model as the first step. The measurement model with 4 latent constructs measured by 20 items was evaluated using Structural Equation Model (SEM). The measurement model revealed acceptable measures that exceeded the recommending threshold values of model fit (RAMSE < 0.08, GFI ≥ 0.80; CFI ≥ 0.90; NFI ≥ 0.90; and IFI ≥ 0.90). The second step is to measure the validity of the proposed model in order to evaluate the reliability of the survey instrument used through utilizing Cronbach's alpha test and Confirmatory Factor Analysis test (CFA). Cronbach's alpha is one of the most widely used tests of reliability; it also used to measure how well a collection of items describe a single latent variable. Statistical resources reported that the lowest acceptable value of Chronbach's alpha is 0.60 and the recommended value is above 0.80 (Hair et al., 2006). Table 3 depicts the results of the reliability test, where the values of Cronbach's alpha ranged from 0.76 to 0.87, where they exceed the lowest acceptable threshold. Moreover, Confirmatory factor analysis was utilized to validate the proposed model. Such test was conducted according to the measures of convergent and discriminant validity indicators. As revealed in Table 3, all of the scale items are significant and exceeded the acceptable threshold value of 50%. Average variance extracted (AVE) is a major technique that could be used to investigate the discriminant validity. Table 4 depicts AVE for all of the model's constructs, where all the constructs explained more than 50% of the variance and ranged from 0.66 to 0.89 and exceeded the recommended value (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Based on that, as showed in Table 4, discriminant validity was revealed since the AVE values were greater than the squared correlations between the variables. Thus, both convergent and discriminant validity of the model's variables were occurred.

Table 3: CFA Analysis Result and Validity and Reliability Measures

Constructs	Code	Factor	Composite	AVE	Cronbach's
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		Loadings	Reliability		alpha
Outsourcing	OUT1	0.81	0.88	0.73	0.77
	OUT2	0.66			
	OUT3	0.75			
	OUT4	0.69			
	OUT5	0.88			
Organizational Structure	OS1	0.64	0.90	0.66	0.76
	OS2	0.67			
	OS3	0.79			
	OS4	0.59			
	OS5	0.81			
Organizational Culture	OC1	0.81	0.84	0.79	0.80
	OC2	0.73			
	OC3	0.66			
	OC4	0.84			
	OC5	0.62			
Job Performance	JP1	0.80	0.91	0.89	0.87
	JP2	0.83			
	JP3	0.79			
	JP4	0.77			
	JP5	0.84			

Table 4: Discriminant Validity Assessment

Construct	OUT	OS	OC	JP
OUT	0.73	0.19	0.21	0.25
OS		0.66	0.32	0.19
OC			0.79	0.13
JP				0.89

4.2 Structural Model and Hypothesis Testing

In order to test the structural research model; it's necessary to refer to model indices as depicted in Table 5. Such indices showed an acceptable goodness of fit to the observed data.

Table 5: Structural Model Fit

Chi sq/df	RMSEA	GFI	CFI	NFI	IFI
1.89	0.057	0.874	0.922	0.903	0.934

The results of path analysis showed a full support to all direct structural paths. Specifically, the outsourcing was significant in improving job performance of employees ($\beta = 0.29$, $p < 0.05$), organizational structure ($\beta = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$), and organizational culture ($\beta = 0.51$, $p < 0.001$). Organizational structure was also found to be positively linked to job performance ($\beta = 0.36$, $p < 0.05$). Also, the path linking organizational culture to job performance was significant ($\beta = 0.36$, $p < 0.05$). The findings of hypothesis testing are depicted in Table 6.

Table 6: Testing Hypotheses -Direct Relationships

Hypothesis	Path	β	CR	P-Value	Result
H1	 OUT → JP	0.29	2.11	*	Supported
H2	 OUT → OS	0.42	4.91	***	Supported
H3	OS JP	0.36	3.17	*	Supported
H5	 OUT → OC	0.51	6.29	***	Supported
H6	OC JP	0.33	8.89	*	Supported

(***: $p < 0.005$, *: $p < 0.05$) (β): path coefficient, OUT: outsourcing, JP: job performance, OS: organizational structure, OC: organizational

culture. Path = Relationship between independent variable on dependent variable; C.R = Critical ration; P = Level of significance.

In addition, this study tests the mediating impact of both organizational structure and organizational culture on job performance. According to Hair et al., (2010), if the value of indirect impact is greater than the value of direct impacts, then a full mediator occurred. In contrast, if the value of direct impact is greater than the value of indirect impact, then it is not considered a mediator. Table 7 shows the findings of mediated path-analysis test, where the impact of outsourcing on job performance is fully mediated by organizational structure and organizational culture.

Table 7: Test of Mediation

Path	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Mediating
OUT-OS-JP	0.003	0.015	Mediating
OUT-OC-JP	0.023	0.049	Mediating

Discussion

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effects of using outsourcing on job performance and the mediating effect of organizational structure and organizational culture on job performance. Structural equation modelling was utilized to test the seventh research hypotheses proposed in this research. The hypothesis that a positive relationship exists between outsourcing and job performance confirming to H1 that proposed in this study. Thus, H1 was supported in the proposed structural model. This finding revealed that outsourcing is one of the effective strategies that might utilize to improve employees' performance. This result confirms the findings with previous empirical evidence conducted by (Andersen et al., 2016; Gyeo & Shinwoo, 2020; Lee et al., 2019). Furthermore, the hypothesis that a positive relationship exists between outsourcing and organizational structure confirming to the hypothesis proposed in this paper. Then, H2 was supported. This finding approved that outsourcing plays a vital role in decision making process and help to write a guide of rules and procedures. This result corresponds with the findings of previous empirical evidence conducted by (Harper, 2015; Burke, 2017). Moreover, the hypothesis that a positive association exists between outsourcing and organizational culture asserting to the hypothesis presented in this research. Consequently, H5 was supported. This means that outsourcing is considered as a strategy that might lead to change the values and norms of employees. Thus, organizational culture should be taken into consideration as one of the main pillars during the implementation of outsourcing strategies (McIvor, 2005). This result confirms the findings with previous studies conducted by (Engelen et al., 2014; Iljins et al., 2015; Omazić & Sopta, 2017). In line with previous studies, the hypotheses that a job performance is positively influenced by organizational structure and organizational culture, conforms to the hypotheses of this research. Thus, H3 and H6 were supported. Initially, Kamiali (2014) argued that flexible structure is considered as effective approach to improve job performance that allows employees to share knowledge easily. Furthermore, Shani(2009) reported that there are structural factors influencing positively on job performance such as innovation, training, technology, tactics, growth and control. Such factors should be incorporated with organizational process to improve job performance. On the other hand, organizational culture was founded to be a predictor of job performance. This means that organizations should be highly focused on organizational culture as a firm-level resource through motivating and supporting employees, guiding employees' behaviour and unifying them toward the common goals of organization. Such result confirms the outcomes of research conducted by Theresia et al.,(2018) and Kyoung and Sunyoung (2019). Finally, the findings of mediation analysis revealed that the influence of outsourcing on job performance is fully mediated by organizational structure and organizational culture. Therefore, H4 and H7 were supported. These findings concur with results of previous empirical evidence. For example, the result of Pablo and Ding (2017) suggest a mediating role of organizational structure on the relationship between outsourcing and employees job performance, where organizational structure is considered as an effective approach that enabling employees to acquire and share knowledge needed to conduct their duties. Moreover, the finding of Al-Junidi (2020) suggests a mediating role of organizational culture on the relationship between outsourcing and job performance.

Conclusion And Implications

Focusing on using outsourcing is become more important for firms in present, especially in Jordan telecommunication sector in order to help employees to enhance and improve their job performance. Most of Jordan telecommunication firms' managers started to recognizes the importance of enhancing job performance in the goal of improving services and products. The research main goal provides other researches with more additional and valuable information about the effects of using outsourcing about the ability of outsourcing and their effects on job performance. The main result of this research is matched with previous studies and reviews which acknowledged and confirmed the ability of outsourcing on improving job performance through its effects

on developing organizational structure and culture. The study also provides future research some recommendations to study the effects of outsourcing on other firms' dimensions such as technological infrastructure, cost, and business processes which will make all those studies offering more valuable information for researches and firms.

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